

EFFECT OF RECYCLING ON THE PROCESSING PARAMETERS AND PROPERTIES OF POST- CONSUMER THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Two distinct polyethylene systems were chosen for this examination. The High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) samples include; injection molding, blown film, and injection blow molding grades. The Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE) samples included; blown film and stretch film grades. Samples of virgin material, 100% recycled resins and 25% recycled resins were analyzed. The processing characteristics evaluated were; Bulk Density, MFI, and Differential Scanning Calorimetry. Tensile properties, were used to evaluate the mechanical performance. The results indicate that for a single resin, recycling does not alter the processing parameters and properties significantly.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

In the United States, the thermoplastic waste constitutes about 5 % of total solid waste stream [1]. The largest fraction of this is made up of various grades of Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) since products made from these are considered "disposable" [2]. Several studies have documented the projected use of these polymers [1-4]. The use of the major recyclable thermoplastics (PET, PE, PVC, PP and PS) was 42 billion pounds in 1990. Of these only about 475 million pounds were recycled in 1989 (the last year for which data is available). This should be compared to the much higher recycling rates for iron and steel (33 %) and for aluminum (25 % including 63 % recycling of aluminum containers) [3]. The best estimates on the projected recycling rates for thermoplastics are between 12 and 25 % by the year 2000. This would imply recycling between 7 and 14 billion pounds of plastics.

It should be pointed out that the broad recycling industry and its economics are governed, to a large extent, by regulatory and social factors. However, the success of aluminum recycling industry has clearly shown that technological and scientific advances can make a significant impact on the economics of recycling. Several factors control the economics of using recycled materials. Two important technological considerations are improvement of the material processing, including reduction of processing cost and the improvements in the materials performance. An overriding factor for the recycling industry is the consistency and reliability of

the materials since these materials directly compete with virgin materials [2]. Two distinct approaches exist to ensure reliability. One view is that the waste polymers be separated, cleaned and refined back into resins that closely resemble the virgin material [5]. The other approach is that since the waste stream contains mixtures of plastics, effective use of commingled mixtures has the potential of drastically reducing the cost of recycled materials via elimination of the very expensive sorting process [6]. The technical literature on both these approaches is rather sparse. While the first approach has the potential of producing reliable materials, its economics will be favorable only if significant savings are achieved in reducing the processing cost. In addition, the inter and intra lot variability for recycled materials is a concern to users. The second approach will be successful if a thorough understanding of the processing and properties of mixed plastics is developed.

In this paper, we have focused on the first approach. We compare the processing parameters and the properties of recycled virgin Polyethylenes. We have also examined the inter and intra lot variability in processing parameters. Various grades of Polyethylenes are the most widely used commodity thermoplastics [1,2] and hence the primary post consumer resins (PCR) of interest.

Two distinct Polyethylene (PE) systems were chosen for this examination. High Density PE (HDPE) and Low Density PE (LDPE). The HDPE samples include; injection molding, blown film, and injection blow molding grades. The LDPE samples included; blown film and stretch film grades. For both systems, batches of virgin material, 100% PC resins and in some cases mixtures of 25% PCR and 75% virgin resin were evaluated. Virgin resin for both LDPE and HDPE was obtained from a national supplier in three separate batches obtained from the same lot. The PC resins were obtained from regional suppliers in batch quantities. In the next section, the experimental procedure is outlined. The results are presented and discussed in Section III and important conclusions presented in Section IV.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The resins used were :	High Density Injection Molding Grade	(HDPE-IM)
	High Density Blow Molding Grade	(HDPE-BM)
	High Density Blown Film Grade	(HDPE-BF)
	Low Density Blown Film Grade	(LDPE-BF)

Table 1. lists the various samples that were tested and their sample ID. In order to compare the inter and intra lot variabilities, samples for testing consisted of 3 samples from a single lot, and 1 sample from two other lots. Sample sizes were 3 pounds except for a 25 pound sample from the first lot. Inter and intra lot variability was assessed by measuring the melt flow index and density, from the various inter and intra lot samples. From the 25 pound sample, tensile test specimens were injection molded.

The melt flow index (MFI) was measured in accordance with ASTM #D1238. Prior to testing, the melt flow indexer was allowed to reach temperature and idle at the desired temperature for 30 minutes. Melt flow index measurements were conducted on samples of approximately 10 g. A 2.16 kg load, and 190°C temperature were used as test conditions. The results varied by as much as 2% due to manual cut time errors. At least, five measurements were conducted for each sample.

Table 1. Sample Listing

RESIN	SAMPLE ID	DESCRIPTION
HDPE-IM	HDR-IM1	PCR Injection Molding Grade
HDPE-IM	HDR-IM2	100% PCR HDPE-IM
HDPE-IM	HDV-IM3	Virgin Injection Molding HDPE
HDPE-BM	HDR-BM1	100% PCR HDPE-BM
HDPE-BM	HDR-BM2	25% PCR HDPE-BM
HDPE-BM	HDV-BM3	Virgin Blow Molding HDPE
HDPE-BM	HDR-BM4	100% PCR HDPE-BM
HDPE-BM	HDR-BM5	100% PCR HDPE-BM
HDPE-BF	HDR-BF1	25% PCR HDPE-BF
HDPE-BF	HDR-BF2	100% PCR HDPE-BF
HDPE-BF	HDR-BF3	PCR HDPE-BF
HDPE-BF	HDV-BF4	Virgin Blown Film HDPE
HDPE-BF	HDV-BF5	Virgin Blown Film HDPE
LDPE-BF	LDR-BF1	100% PCR LDPE-BF
LDPE-BF	LDR-BF2	25% PCR LDPE-BF
LDPE-BF	LDR-BF3	100% PCR LDPE Stretch Film
LDPE-BF	LDV-BF4	Virgin Blown Film LDPE

The density measurements were made in accordance with ASTM #D792. Density measurements were performed on specimens which had been extruded at 190°C and 10 kg from the melt flow indexer. Due to entrapped bubbles within the extrudate error of up to 0.2% are possible. Density was measured on at least five samples.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was conducted on all samples on a Thermal Analysis instrument. DSC was conducted in a nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 5°C/ minute over a temperature span of 40 to 200°C.

Samples for mechanical properties measurements were prepared by injection molding. The die was a three cavity mold which had tensile, flexural, and impact specimens. Injection molding was performed at Plastic Molded Products in Tacoma, WA. Samples were molded using a barrel temperature of 215°C and an identical injection pressure for all samples. The water cooled mold was at a temperature of 18°C. All tensile, flexural, and impact specimens were conditioned at 22°C and 50% humidity for at least 48 hours prior to testing.

Tensile tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM #D638. These tests were conducted only on the blown film grades. Specimens were of the type I geometry. The specimens were clamped with a grip pressure of 12 MPa. Testing was performed at a speed of 20 mm/minute. Load, displacement, and strain data was recorded every second during testing. The LDPE samples did not initially fail within the 163mm travel limit of the testing system, but additional testing on a different load frame allowed the ultimate and failure strength of the LDPE specimens to be determined. Errors in tensile testing are associated with accurately measuring the slope within the elastic range due to the limited elastic range of each sample tested.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III.1 Processing Parameters

For PE, two important molecular parameters are the molecular weight and the degree of crystallinity. These control the processing and properties of the Polyethylene. In this study the parameters were indirectly measured. The MFI provides information about the molecular weight, while the density of the PE depends upon the degree of crystallinity. Finally, the calorimetric measurements provide information about the uniformity of the molecular structure.

The density measurements were quite reproducible with typical standard deviation less than 0.3% of the average value. The intra and inter lot variation in density was insignificant. The average densities are plotted in Fig. 1. The LDPE resins have density values between 0.917 and 0.922 gm/cm³. The generally low density of these resins implies a rather low volume fraction of crystallinity which is to be expected for Low Density Polyethylene. As expected, the HDPEs displayed the highest density. Sample HDR-BF1 is a Medium Density Polyethylene (from DSC). The density of this sample falls between that of the HD and LD resins. For other HDPE resins, the density ranges from 0.947 to 0.959 gm/cm³. Within this group, the blow molding (BM), or blown film (BF) grades have highest density and the injection molding (IM) grades the lowest. For Polyethylene, the density is measure of the crystallinity of the polymer. The mechanical properties (strength, modulus, etc.) are strongly dependent on the density. This correlation will be established in the next sub-sections.

In Fig. 2 the average MFI is plotted for the different resins. For a given resin, the standard deviation is less than 5% of the average value. From these results some general conclusions can be drawn. The measured MFI between different resin grades follows the expected trends. Thus the MFIs for HDPE-IM grade are higher than those for HDPE-BM or HDPE-BF grade. There is no systematic difference between the virgin and PCR resins. As a broad generalization, it was observed that the standard deviation for virgin resins were the lowest (of the order of 1%) while those for PCRs were higher. The standard deviations within a lot and between lots were of the same order of magnitude as the standard deviation between tests from the same sample. The only exception was sample HDR-IM2, for which the inter lot variation was significantly higher than the intra lot variation. This sample also had an unusually high MFI as seen from Fig. 2.

Figure 1. Sample Density

Figure 2. Melt Flow Index

The focus of the DSC data analysis was on the melting profile and the identification of mixed resins. The temperatures and the widths of the melting transitions were used to identify the resin content and its crystalline character. Multiple peaks were an indication of mixed resins. For a majority of the samples, the difference between virgin, 100% PCR and 25% PCR virgin resins was small. The peak position was dependent on the density of the sample. The approximate melting transition for HDPE, MDPE and LDPE were at 130°C, 125°C and 110°C respectively. A representative example is shown in Fig. 3a. It is a DSC scan of a 25% PC and 75% virgin blown film grade PE resin. It shows a very sharp transition at about 125°C. From DSC it can be calculated that this is a MDPE with very uniform crystallinity. Its density was measured to be 0.9336 g/cm³ (Fig. 1) which is typical for MDPE.

Figure 3. DSC Scan of 25% and 75% Virgin PE

The greater strength of the calorimetric technique is in identifying mixed resin systems. This point is illustrated in Fig. 3b. This sample is a 25% PC and 75% virgin low density blown film grade PE. (LDR-BF2). However from the DSC scan, it is clear that it is a mixture of very poorly crystallized LDPE (broad peak at about 110°C) and moderately crystalline MDPE (sharper peak at 122°C). Its density is within experimental error of the low density blown film PEs. However, while others are single resin systems, this one is a mixed resin system.

III.2 Tensile Properties

The tensile tests were conducted in order to investigate the effect of recycling on mechanical properties. An additional goal was to establish correlations between the mechanical properties and processing parameters, that may be easily measured (e.g. density, MFI). The tests were conducted on high density and low density blown film grade polyethylenes. Fig. 4a is a representative plot from a high density polyethylene. The tensile behavior of the resins is characterized by a significant load drop after the peak load. Also shown in Fig. 4a are the relevant properties that can be obtained for the resins from the tensile stress-strain response.

Fig. 4b is representative stress-strain behavior for a low density resin. Note that for these resins the ultimate and the failure point are the same. From a design prospective, the post-yield behavior is of little significance. We will therefore, focus our discussions on the elastic performance. In particular we will focus on the tensile modulus and yield stress. For a given sample, the results were highly reproducible (standard deviation less than 2%). The modulus and the yield stress for the HDPE are higher than those for LDPE with the MDPE values in between, as expected. The tensile modulus and the yield stress are summarized in Fig 5.

Excellent correlation exists between the density (and hence the crystallinity) and the modulus. The correlation can be written as:

$$\log E = \log E^0 + C_0 (\text{density}) \quad (1)$$

where, E^0 and C_0 are equal to 18.24 MPa and 22.3 MPa/g/cm³ respectively.

Figure 4a. Stress-Strain Curve of HDPE Blown Film

Figure 4b. LDPE Blown Film Tensile Test

Figure 5. Summary of Tensile Property Data

Similar correlation exists between the density and the yield stress and this can be written as:

$$Y = Y^0 + K_0 (\text{density}) \quad (2)$$

where, Y^0 and K_0 are equal to 465.2 MPa and 422.4 MPa/g/cm³ respectively. The yield strain for the LDPEs is higher than those for the HDPEs. This is due to the lower modulus of the LDPE. The ultimate tensile strength also increases as the density of the Polyethylene increases.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

From this study, the following conclusion can be drawn. First, it was shown that, in general, the intra and inter lot variations were not significant (with the exception of sample HDR-IM2). Second, for Polyethylenes, the recycled resins were comparable in processing characteristics and performance to the virgin resins. Third, the MFI is a sensitive measure of the grade of the resin (i.e. blow molding, injection molding etc.). Finally, from the tensile data, it can be concluded that the density of the PE resin controls the tensile properties. As the density increases, the modulus, yield stress and ultimate tensile strength increase but the elongation at failure decreases. In this research we were able to demonstrate the added benefits of more advanced materials characterization techniques like Differential Scanning Calorimetry for characterization of mixed systems. In summary, the processing characteristics and properties of recycled PE resins are comparable to virgin resins. Simple tests (e.g. density and MFI) can be used for quality control. DSC can be used for detailed characterization (e.g. uniformity of crystallinity and for identification of components of a mixed resin system) if needed.

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